

CIRCULAR BUSINESS MODEL BLUEPRINT FOR SUSTAINABLE PLASTIC FOOD PACKAGING (2025-2040)

PROBLEM ENCOUNTERED AND OBJECTIVE

The current plastic food packaging industry is a major contributor to environmental pollution and resource depletion. Traditional packaging methods generate excessive waste, with limited circularity in design and production. In response, the blueprint aims to establish a circular business model that significantly reduces plastic waste by applying the "5 Rs": Refuse, Reduce, Redesign, Reuse, and Recycle. The overarching objective is to align with the EU Packaging and Packaging Waste Directive while fostering innovation in packaging design, material use, and waste management. Through a structured approach, the blueprint provides a clear framework for transitioning towards a sustainable, efficient, and scalable circular economy in the food packaging sector.

MAIN RESULTS / OUTCOMES

The blueprint produced in the STOPP project outlines five key objectives for sustainable packaging. It aims to eliminate unnecessary plastic, design fully recyclable packaging, and increase recycled content to reduce reliance on virgin plastics. Expanding reusable packaging systems through standardisation and shared infrastructure is another priority. Additionally, improving collection and sorting ensures materials are effectively recovered and reused. These measures will create a resilient packaging industry aligned with regulatory and consumer sustainability demands.

PRACTICAL RECOMMENDATIONS

Manufacturers should prioritise packaging-free solutions and redesign products to use fewer materials. Policymakers must enforce recycled content regulations and phase out single-use plastics. Investments in recycling technology and waste management are essential. Consumer education and incentives will encourage reusable packaging adoption. Collaboration among industry, regulators, and consumers is key to achieving a sustainable circular packaging system.

Further information

The full report can be found on <https://stopp-project.eu/readiness-tools-resources/>

About this abstract

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STOPP is a Horizon Europe project aiming to transform food plastic packaging through the "5 Rs": Refuse, Reduce, Redesign, Reuse, and Recycle. Aligned with the EU's Packaging Directive, it develops training materials and strategies to promote circular economy solutions. Engaging stakeholders, STOPP advances recycling, reusable packaging, and consumer awareness for sustainable food packaging.

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